

Present Status of E-Human Resource Management Practices and Challenges in Indian Industries

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Abstract:

Despite the multiple benefits associated with the use of digital technologies in the area of HRM, its adoption is not widespread. The limited resources with the developing and the under-developed nations make E-HRM imperative to reduce the organizations operational costs. But before its successful adoption, the challenges to E-HRM need to be overcome and the way forward should be clear. While India is on the path of embracing digital revolution in all spheres of administration and management, its journey is not smooth as societal, cultural, infrastructural and economical barriers impede E-HRM adoption. In this context the present paper highlights the present status, challenges, and future prospects of e-HRM in India with the purpose of providing a pathway to the policy makers and the organizations regarding the successful adoption and implementation of e-HRM practices in India.

Key- Words: E-HRM, Human resource management, ICTs, Digital technologies.

Introduction:

Companies that desire to maintain a competitive edge, both now and in the future require human force well equipped to face the ever increasing pace of technological changes and techniques. This is the accountability of the human force manager to properly train the work force to accomplish the competitive advantages of business in the 21st century. HR managers have moved from handling simple personal issues to making a strategic implementation through supporting the long-term strategies with the necessary employee qualifications and developing the cultural and technical capabilities required for the organization. In recent years, there has been considerable debate regarding human resource management. One must raise the question here as to what should be the priorities for human resources in future? India is now on the cusp of becoming a significant player in the global stage. Everyone wants to do business with us, this change has given a lot of opportunities to our country to grow further but it poses lot of challenges in front of us like Indian companies must gain confidence to acquire foreign giant companies and try to establish themselves competitive vis a vis foreign companies. Also, at the same time we have to give emphasis on the

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various challenges before us like the intellectual gap between people in the corporate world and those in the rural areas - this is becoming a serious concern and the wage differentials between blue collared workers and senior managers, the candidates having good education and communication skills getting more chance in the job market than other people lesser than them, attrition levels are at all-time high in India for example business process outsourcing facing problems with talent retention.

Review of Literature:

The world federation of personnel management association (WFPMA, 2009) survey pointed out the most important top ten HR challenges are leadership development, organizational effectiveness, change management, compensation, health and safety, staff retention, learning and development, succession planning, staffing - recruitment and skilled labor. In the viewpoint of Decenzo and Robins (2001), the most important challenges of HRM are technology, E commerce, work force diversity, globalization and ethical considerations of the organization which may directly or indirectly affect the organization's competitive advantages. Also, technological advancement affects the recruitment, training & development and job performance with great extent which must be studied in the organization.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this research are :

1. To identify the underlying factors and pre- requisites for the success of an e-HRM venture.
2. To identify the challenges associated with the implementation and maintenance of e-HRM systems.
3. To offer recommendations and suggestions for enhancing the effectiveness of e-HRM systems.

Research Methodology and Data Analysis: -

Field Survey-

Research Instruments:

The research instruments used for collecting primary data were:

- Questionnaire and
- Interviews (a patterned interview approach)

The questionnaire (REFERENCE SECTION) comprises of questions pertaining to:-

- Ranking of the possible drivers for introducing e-technology to the HR systems.
- Ranking of the barriers to progress in the e-HRM journey.
- Usage of e-technology for the HR functions. For this purpose, 18 HR functions were specified. These are- Recruitment and Selection, Payroll Management, Leave Management, Attendance Management, Manpower Planning, Communication, Training and Development, Performance Management, Induction, Selecting Benefits, Compensation Planning, Competency Mapping, Career Planning, Succession Planning, Employee Transition, Travel Management, Exit Management and Maintaining Employee Records.
- Usage of HR Service delivery tools like ESS, MSS, Web 2.0, Intranet and e-Learning Portal.
- Nature of Sourcing solutions adopted by companies for enabling e-technology to HR systems- In-house/Outsourced/ Software-as-a-service.
- Perception of respondents on a five-point scale regarding their company's position in the e-HRM journey today vs after 5 years. The scale ranges from 'Neither understand nor value e- HRM' to 'complete incorporation of e-HRM strategy into the business model'.

Sampling Design:

The analysis of data is based on the following classification:

Services Sector including- Accounting/Consulting/Taxation ; Airlines & Aviation; Banks; Export Houses; Financial Services; High- tech Services; Hospitals/Healthcare; Hotels/Resorts; Insurance; Law/Legal Consultants; Management/Engineering /Environment Consultants; Media/Entertainment;

Mutual Fund/Stock Broking; Office Automation; Placement /HR Training Consultants; Retail; Security; Travel & Tourism.

Statement of Hypotheses:

H01: There is no significant difference between groups and within group’s w.r.t. the considered driver for introducing e-HRM systems in companies.

H02: There is no significant difference in usage of e-technology for the considered HR function between Services vs Manufacturing groups.

H03: There is no significant difference in the usage of e-technology for the considered HR function between MNC vs Non-MNC groups.

Table-1

% of Respondents by Type of Sector
(Services/Manufacturing)

	Frequency	Percent
Services	344	34.40
Manufacturing	656	65.60
TOTAL	1000	100.00

Table-2

% of Respondents by Type of Company
(MNC/Non-MNC)

	Frequency	Percent
MNC	170	17.00
Non-MNC	830	83.00
TOTAL	1000	100.00

Table-3

% of Respondents (MNC/Non-MNC) *(Services/Manufacturing)

Type of Company		Type of Sector		Total
		Services	Manufacturing	
MNC	Count	110	60	170
	% within Type of Sector	31.98%	9.15%	17.00%
Non-MNC	Count	234	596	830
	% within Type of Sector	68.02%	90.85%	83.00%
Total	Count	344	656	1000
	% within Type of Sector	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Table-4

% of Respondents by Size of Company
(Annual Turn-over)

Annual Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Frequency	Percent
<= 10 Crores	92	9.20
10-100 Crores	367	36.70
100-250 Crores	187	18.70
250-500 Crores	105	10.50
500- 1000 Crores	109	10.90
1000-2500 Crores	77	7.70
2500-5000 Crores	34	3.40
> 5000 Crores	29	2.90
Total	1000	100.00

Table-5

% of Respondents by Size of Company
(No. of Employees)

No. of Employees	Frequency	Percent
101-250	172	17.20
251-500	166	16.60
501-1000	340	34.00
1001-2500	172	17.20
2501-5000	68	6.80
> 5000	82	8.20
Total	1000	100.00

Table-6

Size of Company (Annual Turn-over) * Type of Sector
(Services/Manufacturing)

Annual Turn-over (Rs. Cr.)		Type of Sector		Total
		Services	Manufacturing	
<= 10 Crores	Count	81	11	92
	% within Type of Sector	23.50%	1.70%	9.20%
10-100 Crores	Count	170	197	367
	% within Type of Sector	49.40%	30.10%	36.70%
100-250 Crores	Count	39	148	187
	% within Type of Sector	11.30%	22.60%	18.70%
250-500 Crores	Count	14	91	105
	% within Type of Sector	4.10%	13.90%	10.50%
500- 1000 Crores	Count	20	89	109
	% within Type of Sector	5.80%	13.60%	10.90%
	Count	12	65	77

1000-2500 Crores	% within Type of Sector	3.50%	9.90%	7.70%
	Count	5	29	34
2500-5000 Crores	% within Type of Sector	1.50%	4.40%	3.40%
	Count	3	26	29
> 5000 Crores	% within Type of Sector	0.90%	4.00%	2.90%
	Count	344	656	1000
Total	% within Type of Sector	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Table-7

Size of Company (No. of Employees) * Type of Sector
(Services/Manufacturing)

No. of Employees		Type of Sector		Total
		Services	Manufacturing	
101-250	Count	151	21	172
	% within Type of Sector	43.90%	3.20%	17.20%
251-500	Count	70	96	166
	% within Type of Sector	20.30%	14.70%	16.60%
501-1000	Count	60	280	340
	% within Type of Sector	17.40%	42.70%	34.00%
1001-2500	Count	32	140	172
	% within Type of Sector	9.30%	21.40%	17.20%
2501-5000	Count	19	49	68
	% within Type of Sector	5.50%	7.50%	6.80%
> 5000	Count	12	70	82
	% within Type of Sector	3.50%	10.50%	8.20%

	Sector			
Total	Count	344	656	1000
	% within Type of Sector	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Table-8

Drivers for introducing e-HRM Systems in companies: Mean Ranks by Type of Sector (Services/ Manufacturing)

CONSIDERED DRIVERS	Type of Sector					
	Services		Manufacturing		Total	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
a. Increase Integration within the HR function	7.36	2.02	8.54	1.64	8.14	1.86
b. Encourage open communication and sharing of Information	5.42	2.87	7.29	1.82	6.65	2.40
c. Standardize Systems and Procedures	8.15	1.80	3.08	2.26	4.82	3.20
d. Enable HR cost saving and control	1.54	0.92	1.47	0.84	1.50	0.87
e. Reduce time spent on routine administrative tasks by HR staff	4.37	2.11	3.97	1.61	4.11	1.81
f. Better management of data and information	7.04	1.72	6.78	2.36	6.87	2.17
g. Reduce paper transactions	5.27	2.73	3.13	1.05	3.87	2.08
h. Refocus HR staff on strategic activities	7.13	1.85	7.22	1.58	7.19	1.68
i. Increase overall productivity	5.88	2.45	6.70	2.08	6.42	2.25
j. Improve HR transactions accuracy/speed/Integrity	2.79	1.45	6.81	2.11	5.43	2.68

Table-9

Drivers for introducing e-HRM Systems in companies: Mean Rank Order by Type of Sector (Services/ Manufacturing)

CONSIDERED DRIVERS		MEAN RANK ORDER		
		Services	Manufacturing	TOTAL
a	Increase Integration within the HR function	9	10	10
b	Encourage open communication and sharing of Information	5	9	7
c	Standardize Systems and Procedures	10	2	4
d	Enable HR cost saving and control	1	1	1
e	Reduce time spent on routine administrative tasks by HR staff	3	4	3
f	Better management of data and information	7	6	8
g	Reduce paper transactions	4	3	2
h	Refocus HR staff on strategic activities	8	8	9
i	Increase overall productivities	6	5	6
j	Improve HR transactions accuracy/speed/Integrity	2	7	5

1: Most Important; 10: Least Important

Table-10

Drivers for introducing e-HRM Systems in companies: Mean Ranks by Type of Company (MNC/ Non-MNC)

CONSIDERED DRIVERS	Type of Company					
	MNC		Non-MNC		Total	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.

a. Increase Integration within the HR function	7.37	1.88	8.29	1.82	8.14	1.86
b. Encourage open communication and sharing of Information	3.93	2.58	7.19	1.95	6.65	2.40
c. Standardize Systems and Procedures	7.57	2.05	4.26	3.10	4.82	3.20
d. Enable HR cost saving and control	1.49	0.83	1.50	0.88	1.50	0.87
e. Reduce time spent on routine administrative tasks by HR staff	6.77	2.04	3.57	1.17	4.11	1.81
f. Better management of data and information	7.22	1.53	6.80	2.27	6.87	2.17
g. Reduce paper transactions	6.60	3.29	3.32	1.09	3.87	2.08
h. Refocus HR staff on strategic activities	7.09	2.27	7.21	1.53	7.19	1.68
i. Increase overall productivity	3.37	1.09	7.03	1.90	6.42	2.25
j. Improve HR transactions accuracy/speed/Integrity	3.63	1.13	5.79	2.76	5.43	2.68

Table-11

Drivers for introducing e-HRM Systems in companies: Mean Rank Order by type of Company (MNC/ Non-MNC)

DRIVER S		MEAN RANK		
		MNC	Non-MNC	TOTAL
a	Increase Integration within the HR function	9	10	10
b	Encourage open communication and sharing of Information	4	8	7
c	Standardize Systems and Procedures	10	4	4
d	Enable HR cost saving and control	1	1	1

e	Reduce time spent on routine administrative tasks by HR staff	6	3	3
f	Better management of data and information	8	6	8
g	Reduce paper transactions	5	2	2
h	Refocus HR staff on strategic activities	7	9	9
i	Increase overall productivity	2	7	6
j	Improve HR transactions accuracy/speed/Integrity	3	5	5

1: Most Important; 10: Least Important

Factors affecting the role of HRM:-

Globalization:

Greengard (1995) defined globalization as the system of interaction among the countries of the world in order to develop the global economy. Globalization refers to the amalgamation of economics and societies around the world which means that world trade and financial markets are becoming more integrated.

Technological advances:

Technological advances have a significant impact on HR business practices. Due to the advancements in the technology there has been a drastic change in the approach to the various projects and the scenarios that guide to the organizational regulations.

Workforce Diversity:

Diversity by definition for the business world means having a workforce that represents many different viewpoints, backgrounds and cultures. Diversity affects all areas of organizations from recruitment to compensation, to the affect it has on the corporate culture, morale and competitiveness. Diversity in the workplace is an increasingly topical theme in management.

Changes in political and legal environment:

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If there are changes in the political and legal environment, then almost all aspects of HRM will be affected by the legal and regulatory environment. The key drivers of a political climate include the extent of external regulations, nature of work contracts, various labour legislations and case laws etc.

Innovative practices in HR areas:

1. Recruitment and selection
2. Learning and development
3. Rewards and recognition
4. Career planning
5. Compensation and benefits
6. Performance management
7. Leadership and development
8. Organization structure

1. Recruitment and selection

1. Google:

(i) Diversity among employees: Ex – army man to former school teacher in the workforce.
(ii) For recruitment they expect the person has to be comfortable with technology and be optimistic about the future. “Like someone who you would find interesting on a long train journey”. The company’s recruitment process ensures that it gets the people edge it needs. There is a battery of wiring tests, interviews are rigorous, not in the sense of being a stress interview, but interviewers try and go deep into what makes the candidate tick. Then the detailed feedback on the candidate is given to an independent team in charge of hiring. The company’s credo is to hire someone who is better than you.

2. Employee referrals by employees which comprises 50% of all hiring at SAP Labs India, Bangalore.

3. Non – standard pool of talent: housewives with a gap in career

2. Learning and development

SME's (Subject Matter Experts):

HR team identifies the internal subject matter experts to give training to the employees.
Sending employees for higher studies

E-Welcome:

When employees join the company, they have to interact with functionaries in other regions who assume that the new person knows the internal systems. Often the new employee is unfamiliar with the systems and is at sea. The E-Welcome gateway lists certain universal systems of the company and helps them get familiar with such things. A stand – out feature is that if this checklist remains incomplete it sends an automatic notice to the manager responsible for the employee.

Company follows a training policy to have seven days of training every year is mandatory for all employees, even this chairman and the directors.

GOLD (Godrej Organization for Learning and Development):

Web-based learning tied up with UK – based NetG to distribute e- learning modules among the workforce. The company gives equal importance to soft skill training. “ Out of box thinking is more important “, the sponsored the Edward De Bono certification of lateral thinking for two of its managerial employees, so they could teach in – house. This learning creates a leadership pipeline.

3. Rewards and recognition

1. MAD (Mutual Admiration):

Is an event where every employee is given green cardboard leaves on which they scribble messages of appreciation and pin them onto the MAD tree in the cafeteria. The leaves are a way of reaching out to colleagues and teams who have mattered. And at the end of the week, the foliage gets thick. Surely, the employees like being around each other.

2. Smart Work and Smart Reward:

It's directed towards improving employees productivity. It rewards those who complete tasks in fewer working hours than stipulated. The reward process is well defined and transparent. It has helped in ensuring better work – life balance.

3. Promotion within

4. Career planning

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1. Career Success Centre:

An online portal and a one – stop shop for all career related resources. The portal helps employees plan and develop their careers according to business needs.

5. Compensation and benefits

1. Paternity leave
2. Extra three months maternity leave at half the salary leave
3. No attendance monitoring
4. unlimited sick leave
5. equal privileges for employees across levels: employees at all levels travel in the same class, stay in similar hotels, work out of standard cubicles, log in their own leave.

6. Performance management

1. 360 degree feedback system
2. “Performance Task Force”: A cross functional team constitutes 20 members and this force keeps track of what needs to be plugged, and what seems to be working. It goes back to HR every six months to deliver feedback.

7. Leadership and development

1. Food for thought: Inviting employees in groups to chat with Managing director over lunch in an informal environment on various issues and topics.
2. Succession planning
3. Employee empowerment
4. Reach out: An initiative to keep a direct link of communication to its employees, the president of the company meets the employees.

Summary of the findings: -

In summary, contrasting the initial goals of the company when introducing web-based HR tools (for i.e., E-recruitment system and a part of E-learning program) with the actual changes, it can be concluded that most of them have been fulfilled after more than 5 years of implementation. It is evident that the administrative burden has been lessened where the E-HRM has been practiced (for i.e., the recruitment and selection department). Additionally, an improvement in the perceived quality of services and client satisfaction has been observed. However, no evidence was found of an actual reduction of costs.

Table: A summary of findings.

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Themes	Main findings
<p>The perception of E-HRM</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The unawareness of the term • Challenges to the investment in E-HRM • Practicing conventional HRM rather than E-HRM
<p>The impact of E-HRM on the roles of HR</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low application of HR technology • Recruitment and training as two main areas employing E-HR tools • A shift from administrative expert to employee champion
<p>Line managers' accountability for HR</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High involvement in HR related activities • Willingness to take on HR responsibilities • Technology shows little support to line managers' HR task completion • Line managers' expectation of E-HRM implementation

Conclusions:

In the present competitive world, the companies are facing lot of skill shortage, talent crunch and attrition reached historically height ever, that made the companies feel that internal talent is also important equally as external talent, so every company is trying to devise innovative HR practices to attract best talent, giving them nice environment to work, enabling the company to retain talent. The above said practices are being conceived / implemented and being found successful by the leading companies in India. If a company wishes to enhance its competitiveness in the global market, it can benefit from adopting the converging HR practices observed across different companies in various areas.

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